

the

best

Journal of Politics and Development

ISSN 2632-4911

Volume 15 ■ Number 2 ■ Summer 2025

the rest: journal of politics and development

Previously published as Journal of Global Analysis (JGA)

Editors-in-Chief:

Ozgur TUFEKCI, Assoc. Prof. | Karadeniz Technical University, Türkiye & CESRAN International
Rahman DAG, Assoc. Prof. | Marmara University, Türkiye & CESRAN International

Associate Editors:

Alessia CHIRIATTI, Dr. | Istituto Affari Internazionali, Italy
Marco MARSILI, Dr. | Ca' Foscari University, Italy & CESRAN International

Assistant Editors:

Ekrem OK | Agri Ibrahim Cecen University, Türkiye & CESRAN International
Rabia BUYUKPINAR | Zonguldak Bulent Ecevit University, Türkiye & CESRAN International

Editorial Board

Sener AKTURK, Prof. | Koç University, Turkey
Enrique ALBEROLA, Prof. | Banco de España, Spain
Mustafa AYDIN, Prof. | Kadir Has University, Turkey
Ian BACHE, Prof. | University of Sheffield, UK
Kee-Hong BAE, Prof. | York University, Canada
Mark BASSIN, Prof. | Sodertorn University, Sweden
Alexander BELLAMY, Prof. | Uni. of Queensland, Australia
Richard BELLAMY, Prof. | Uni. College London, UK
Andreas BIELER, Prof. | University of Nottingham, UK
Pinar BILGIN, Prof. | Bilkent University, Turkey
Ken BOOTH, Prof. | Aberystwyth University, UK
Stephen CHAN, Prof. | SOAS, University of London, UK
Nazli CHOUCRI, Prof. | MIT, USA
Judith CLIFTON, Prof. | Universidad de Cantabria, Spain
John M. DUNN, Prof. | University of Cambridge, UK
Kevin DUNN, Prof. | Hobart and William Smith Colleges, USA
Can ERBIL, Assoc. Prof. | Boston College, USA
Stephen Van EVERA, Prof. | MIT, USA
Marc FLEURBAEY, Prof. | Princeton University, USA
Bulent GOKAY, Prof. | Keele University, UK
Ayla GOL, Prof. | York St John University, UK
Stefano GUZZINI, Prof. | Uppsala Universitet, Sweden

David HELD, Prof. | London Sch. of Economics, LSE, UK
Tony HERON, Prof. | University of York, UK
Raymond HINNEBUSCH, Prof. | Uni. of St Andrews, UK
John M. HOBSON, Prof. | University of Sheffield, UK
Michael KENNY, Prof. | University of Sheffield, UK
Cécile LABORDE, Prof. | University College London, UK
Scott LUCAS, Prof. | University of Birmingham, UK
Kalypto NICOLAIDIS, Prof. | University of Oxford, UK
Ziya ONIS, Prof. | Koc University, Turkey
Alp OZERDEM, Prof. | George Mason University, USA
Danny QUAH, Prof. | London School of Economics, UK
José Gabriel PALMA, Prof. | Cambridge University, UK
Jenik RADON, Prof. | Columbia University, USA
Oliver RICHMOND, Prof. | University of Manchester, UK
Ibrahim SIRKECI, Prof. | Regent's College London, UK
Ian TAYLOR, Prof. | University of St Andrews, UK
Ali WATSON, Prof. | University of St Andrews, UK
Brian WHITE, Prof. | University of Sheffield, UK
Stefan WOLFF, Prof. | University of Birmingham, UK
Biroł YESILADA, Prof. | Portland State University, USA
Hakan YILMAZKUDAY, Prof. | Florida International University, USA

The Rest: Journal of Politics and Development is published on behalf of the Centre for Strategic Research and Analysis (CESRAN) as an academic e-journal. The articles are brought into use via the website of the journal (<https://therestjournal.com/>). CESRAN and the Editors of The Rest: Journal of Politics and Development do not expect that readers of the review will sympathise with all the sentiments they find, for some of our writers will flatly disagree with others. It does not accept responsibility for the views expressed in any article, which appears in The Rest: Journal of Politics and Development.

** The surnames are listed in alphabetical order.*

the rest: journal of politics and development

Previously published as Journal of Global Analysis (JGA)

INDEXING & ABSTRACTING

- Academic Index
- Bielefeld Academic Search Engine (BASE)
- Columbia International Affairs Online (CIAO)
- Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ)
- EBSCO Publishing Inc.
- EconLit
- EconPapers
- Genamics JournalSeek
- IDEAS
- Index Islamicus
- Infomine
- International Bibliography of Book Reviews of Scholarly Literature in the Humanities and Social Sciences (IBR)
- International Bibliography of Periodical Literature in the Humanities and Social Sciences (IBZ)
- International Bibliography of the Social Sciences (IBSS)
- International Relations and Security Network (ISN)
- Lancaster Index to Defence & International Security Literature
- Peace Palace Library
- Research Papers in Economics (RePEc)
- Social Sciences Information Space (SOCIONET)
- Ulrich's Periodicals Directory

TABLE OF CONTENTS

RESEARCH ARTICLES

- 152** **India in a Changing Global Order: Geopolitical Challenges and Strategic Interests in the Indo-Myanmar Borderlands**
By Manashi Parashar
- 163** **The Evolution of Japan's Limited Sovereignty: From the Era of Unequal Treaties to the Japan-U.S. Alliance**
By Yukio Sakurai
- 182** **Liberty, Affect, and The Rise of Populism**
By Colin Anthony Smith MacNairn
- 198** **The Emergence of Hybrid Warfare and the Future of Global Security: A Comparative Study of Russian and NATO's Hybrid Infrastructure in Ukraine**
By Shahzada Rahim Abbas
- 213** **Implications of Military Aid on Global Arms Sales and Production**
By Zekeri Momoh
- 225** **A New Model for Measuring the Human Development Index: A Comparison of the Organisation of Turkic States and the EU**
By Abdullah Zübeyr Şekerci
- 245** **The Adaptation of Land Forces to the New Multipolar Order**
By Ricardo J Vieira
- 259** **Parliamentary Diplomacy and Ontological (In)Security in Small States**
By Nádia Teresa dos Santos
- 276** **Education and Africa's Structural Transformation: Human Capital, Partnerships, and the Case for a Pan-African Movement**
By Pedro Silva Baptista
- 298** **Revisiting Alexis de Tocqueville's Civil Society Concept from a Political-Economic Perspective**
By Ali Erdem Başçoban
- 311** **Overtourism: A Local and International Challenge to the Iberian Peninsula and Italy**
By Maria Antónia Pires de Almeida

International Think-tank www.cesran.org

Consultancy

Research Institute

CESRAN International is headquartered in the UK

CESRAN International is a member of the United Nations Academic Impact (UNAI)

CESRAN International is a think-tank specialising on international relations in general, and global peace, conflict and development related issues and challenges.

The main business objective/function is that we provide expertise at an international level to a wide range of policy making actors such as national governments and international organisations. CESRAN with its provisions of academic and semi-academic publications, journals and a fully-functioning website has already become a focal point of expertise on strategic research and analysis with regards to global security and peace. The Centre is particularly unique in being able to bring together wide variety of expertise from different countries and academic disciplines.

The main activities that CESRAN undertakes are providing consultancy services and advice to public and private enterprises, organising international conferences and publishing academic material.

Some of CESRAN's current publications are:

- THE REST: Journal of Politics and Development (tri-annual, peer reviewed) www.therestjournal.com
- Novus Orbis: Journal of Politics and International Relations (biannual, peer reviewed) www.dergipark.org.tr/en/pub/novusorbis
- Journal of Conflict Transformation and Security (biannual, peer reviewed)
- Political Reflection Magazine (quarterly) www.politicalreflectionmagazine.com (2010-2023)
- CESRAN Paper Series
- CESRAN Policy Brief
- Turkey Focus Policy Brief

CESRAN International also organises an annual international conference since 2014. Until 2023 it was called as “International Conference on Eurasian Politics and Society (IEPAS)”. From 2023, it was renamed as “CESRAN: Annual Conference on International Studies”.

<https://cesranconference.org/>

- **Ranked among the top 150 International think tanks**

Implications of Military Aid on Global Arms Sales and Production

the rest: journal of politics and development
2025 | vol 15(2) | 213-224
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.16882227
www.therestjournal.com

Zekeri Momoh

Dr., Department of Political Science, Karl Kumm University, Nigeria
momohzekeri@gmail.com, <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7938-8738>

KEYWORDS

Conflict Merchants,
United States,
Israel,
Ukraine,
Military Aid,
War

Received March 20, 2025
Revised July 10, 2025
Accepted July 17, 2025

ABSTRACT

This study examines the implications of increasing military aid on arms sales and production. This study adopted the historical research design, with data collected from secondary sources, and content analysis was used for its analysis. The study argues that increasing military aid to especially belligerent states has influenced global arms sales and production. It equally argues that the consequences of the cumulative military aid to Israel and Ukraine include human rights violations, humanitarian crisis, growth in arms production, increasing military budgets and revenue for arms manufacturers, among others. Nevertheless, justifications of the military aid are to ensure the survival of the state and its sovereignty, as well as the survival of the political regime. Lastly, this study recommends, among other things, that the United Nations Security Council should employ a more democratic approach to the ongoing Israel-Gaza war and Russia-Ukraine war to produce a win-win outcome for the interests of international peace and security, as against the interests of conflict profiteers from military aid.

Introduction

The end of World War II in 1945 led to the emergence of the Cold War, which was an ideological war that was characterised by alliance formation, arms races and balance of power. The outcome of WWII paved way for the United States and the Soviet Union as the two dominant powers in the international system under what is popularly called the bipolar system in which the United States and her ally were regarded as the Western bloc, advocating for the capitalist ideology while the Soviet Union and her allies were known as the Eastern bloc and were championing the Socialist/Communist ideology.

It was against this background that the international system was polarised into the capitalist and socialist blocs. Hence, there was an ideological divide between the Western and Eastern blocs. One of the features of the Cold War era was the arms race and hostility between the Eastern and Western blocs. Besides, one of the drivers of the arms race was the use of military aid, military assistance and military support to strengthen the military capabilities of allied nations. Moreover, the United States of America was considered a leading nation in military aid to European and Asian nations considered to be its allies from the 1950s to the 1970s. However, the Soviet Union was also involved in the provision of military aid to its ally during the same period, thereby making the United States and the Soviet Union the leading countries in the provision of military aid during the Cold War era.

Between the 1960s and 1990s, some leading European countries that were members of the North Atlantic Treaty Organisation (NATO), such as Britain, France and Germany, were also involved in the provision of military aid to other NATO member states, such as Turkey and Greece. It is also important to note that NATO member states were also involved in arms transfers to their former colonies. For instance, Britain, France, Belgium and Portugal were also involved in arms transfers and provision of military aid to their former colonies in Africa, Asia and Latin American countries. It can be argued that most former colonies in Africa, Asia and Latin America started their armed forces with the military aid received from their ex-colonisers. For instance, France provided military aid to ex-colonial territories and allies such as Lebanon, Niger, Burkina Faso, Cameroon, Somalia, Tunisia and Uganda, among others. Likewise, Germany provided military aid to countries such as Israel, Greece, Portugal, Turkey, Iraq, Jordan, Syria, Mali, Niger, Nigeria and Tunisia in their fight against terrorism and other security threats (ARA News, 2017; Deutsche Welle, 2016; Dolamari, 2016; William, 2009).

In addition, the United Kingdom also provided military aid to countries such as Afghanistan, Somalia, Iraq and Lebanon. It is pertinent to note that the UK military aid was limited to recipient countries to training and non-lethal equipment to aid military support operations in Nigeria, Somalia and Djibouti among others (Bario, 2013; British Foreign and Commonwealth Office, 2013; British Ministry of Defence, 2016; Hammond, 2016; Ellwood, 2016; Barrington, et al 2016). The reason was attributed to human rights violations committed by security agencies in countries such as Nigeria and Somalia, where innocent civilians are often killed during crossfire with armed militant groups and terrorist network organisations such as Boko Haram, Al-Shabaab, Hizbul Islam, Islamic State in Somalia (ISS), Al-Ittihad al-Islami (AIAI) and Al-Muhajiroun elements, etc.

Moreover, Japan has also provided military aid in recent years to countries such as Malaysia, the Philippines and Vietnam (Dominguez, 2017). Nevertheless, Saudi Arabia has provided military aid in the form of financial assistance to allied nations such as Lebanon for the procurement of arms from France. Furthermore, Iran has provided military aid to armed non-state groups in Lebanon, such as Hezbollah (Hizbullah), Abdullah Azzam Brigades, Fatah al-Islam, Jund al-Sham and ISIS (Islamic State) cells), in Yemen, armed non-state actors include Houthis (Ansar Allah), Al-Qaeda in the Arabian Peninsula (AQAP), Islamic State in Yemen (IS-Y) and Southern Transitional Council (STC) Militants and in Pakistan include Tehrik-i-Taliban Pakistan (TTP), Lashkar-e-Taiba (LeT), Jaish-e-Mohammed (JeM), Haqqani Network, Sipah-e-Sahaba Pakistan (SSP), Islamic State – Khorasan Province (ISKP) and Lashkar-e-Jhangvi (LeJ) (Al-Rasheed 2016; Gay 2014; SIPRI 2012; Wezeman, et al, 2016).

It is important to note that China also has a long-standing role in the provision of military aid across the world (Copper, 2016). For instance, China has provided military aid to countries such as Sri Lanka, Ecuador, Nigeria, Barbados and Cambodia (Badri-Maharaj, 2016; El Universo, 2016; Grevatt, 2016; Peel, et al, 2016; Sokhean, 2016; The Tribune, 2016; Var, 2016). Similarly, very little is known in the literature of International relations and strategic studies about Russia's military aid. Moreover, studies have shown that Russia has provided military aid in the form of military equipment to Afghanistan to bolster security on its southern border against the encroachment of extreme Islamist groups into its territory. Again, Russia has also provided military aid to Kyrgyzstan, Syria and Tajikistan (Gul, 2017; Pannier, 2015). However, there was a drastic decline in military aid to developing countries following the collapse of the Soviet Union in the early 1990s.

In recent years, there has been increasing US military aid to countries such as Afghanistan and Iraq between 2007 and 2016. It is pertinent to note that since 1945, the United States has remained the largest provider of military aid in the world. Also, the United States has the longest military aid programme, especially since the September 11, 2001, terrorist attack in the US. Today, the military aid remains a critical component in the United States' foreign policy since 2006 under the auspices

of what is known as “Building Partner Capacity”, which captures the entire United States national security policy. It is equally important to note that the United States classified arms transfer under its Foreign Military Sales (FMS) programme, which was within the purview of “security assistance” (Moroney et al, 2013; McInnis et al, 2015).

Today, the United States Foreign Military Financing (FMF) programme is known for the procurement of military equipment from the United States defence industry. In addition, the United States is the leading country in the world today in terms of the sales/transfer of arms under the United States Excess Defence Articles (EDA) Grant programme, which provides military hardware and software to Afghanistan, Syria and Iraq, just to mention a few countries in the world. Again, the United States had other programmes that support military aid, especially in training or provision of equipment for non-military institutions, such as the United States International Military Education and Training (IMET) programme, and the US Maritime Security Initiative (MSI). The objectives of the United States security assistance programme such as Excess Defense Articles (EDA), International Military Education and Training (IMET), and Military Sales Initiatives (MSI) are to strengthen partner nations' defense capabilities, promote interoperability, enhance professional military education, and advance U.S. strategic interests globally (Carafano, 2020; Defense Security Cooperation Agency, 2023).

Since its introduction, these programmes have aimed both to increase defence cooperation and to support US foreign policy objectives. Some experts argue that the programme influences military elites in certain countries in line with US strategic interests, suggesting that this may weaken civilian oversight. The programme has at times been controversial, as some US-trained soldiers have participated in military coups in their home countries (Carafano, 2020; Defence Security Cooperation Agency, 2023).

Under the United States Foreign Military Financing (FMF) and Excess Defence Articles (EDA) grant programmes, several countries have benefited from U.S. military aid, each for specific strategic and security reasons. For instance, Egypt remains one of the largest beneficiaries of United States Foreign Military Financing, receiving substantial funding to modernise its armed forces and maintain regional security, especially in its counterterrorism operations in the Sinai Peninsula and to safeguard the Suez Canal, which is an important global trade route (DSCA, 2023).

Similarly, Israel has consistently received the United States Foreign Military Financing assistance to support its military operations in the Middle East. This funding enhances Israel's defensive capabilities against regional adversaries and strengthens Israel's missile defence systems, such as the Iron Dome (Carafano, 2020). Also, Saudi Arabia has benefited from both U.S FMF and EDA programmes. Through the FMF and EDA assistance, Saudi Arabia has acquired advanced defence equipment to secure its borders and counter threats from extremist militant groups and regional rivals. This U.S.-Saudi Arabia cooperation aligns with its objectives in ensuring energy security and stability in the Gulf region (DSCA, 2023). Besides, prior to the U.S. withdrawal in 2021 from Afghanistan, Afghanistan received extensive military support targeted at building its national security forces to combat the Taliban terrorist network and other insurgent groups in Afghanistan, by promoting counterterrorism and regional stability in the Middle East (Carafano, 2020).

In Iraq, United States Foreign Military Financing (FMF) and Excess Defence Articles (EDA) grant programmes provided equipment and training to strengthen the Iraqi military's ability to combat ISIS and secure national borders, thereby supporting U.S. counterterrorism goals in the region (Carafano, 2020). Pakistan received military aid aimed at enhancing its counterterrorism capabilities, particularly in the Federally Administered Tribal Areas (FATA), and supporting its role as a U.S. partner in combating extremist networks (DSCA, 2023).

However, U.S. assistance to Colombia through its Foreign Military Financing (FMF) and Excess Defense Articles (EDA) grant programs was primarily designed to counter-narcotics operations and combating armed insurgent groups such as the Fuerzas Armadas Revolucionarias de Colombia (FARC), which translates to in English means Revolutionary Armed Forces of Colombia (RAFC) which was formed in 1964 as a Marxist-Leninist guerrilla organization with the goal of overthrowing the Colombian government and establishing a communist state, but decades later, FARC was involved in drug trafficking, kidnappings, and extortion. However, in 2016, it signed a historic peace agreement with the Colombian government, officially ending more than 50 years of armed conflict in Colombia, although some dissident factions remain active in Colombia (International Crisis Group, 2017; Serrano, 2019; United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime, 2021). Nevertheless, the cooperation between the U.S and Colombia has contributed to the country's security reforms and stabilisation efforts (DSCA, 2023)

United States Foreign Military Financing (FMF) and Excess Defence Articles (EDA) grant programmes to the Philippines have focused on maritime security, counterterrorism, and improving military readiness, especially in addressing threats from extremist groups such as Abu Sayyaf and maintaining stability in the South China Sea (Carafano, 2020). In Africa, Nigeria has benefited from FMF and EDA support to enhance its fight against Boko Haram and Islamic State West Africa Province (ISWAP), thereby contributing to regional security in the Lake Chad Basin (DSCA, 2023). Overall, these programs reflect U.S. strategic interests in promoting global security, counterterrorism, and defence cooperation with partner nations.

However, U.S. military aid has been subjected to considerable criticism both domestically and internationally. Critics argue that such assistance often serves geopolitical interests rather than purely security or humanitarian objectives. For instance, the United States has faced strong backlash for its continued provision of military aid to Israel, particularly in the context of the Israeli-Palestinian conflict. Many Arab nations, including Yemen and Lebanon, have condemned this support, viewing it as enabling Israeli military operations in Gaza and the West Bank, which they consider violations of human rights and international law (Sharp, 2023). Similarly, U.S. military aid to Ukraine amid its conflict with Russia has been criticised not only by some foreign governments but also by certain political actors within the United States, who argue that such commitments risk escalating the conflict and draining U.S. resources (Carafano, 2020; Congressional Research Service, 2023). These critiques highlight the contentious nature of U.S. security assistance and its implications for international diplomacy and regional stability.

Furthermore, critics have argued that significant numbers of U.S.-supplied military assistance have been redirected toward internal security operations used to suppress political opposition and civil dissent rather than being effectively deployed against terrorist threats such as Boko Haram in Nigeria. The situation was also similar to Afghanistan, where analysts have noted that U.S.-funded military aid was not used as part of its counterterrorism approach and, in some instances, this military aid was used for political patronage networks or factional uses that undermined governance and accountability. Also, U.S. military aid to Colombia was designed basically for counter-narcotics and counterinsurgency operations. However, the U.S. military aid has been criticised, as some of the military aid was used in internal repression or human rights violations (Mulnick et al., 2016; Watts, 2015). In Iraq, the situation is not different, as critics have argued that some U.S. arms to Iraq were used for battlefield capture or in sectarian-motivated security crackdowns rather than in coordinated counterterrorism operations against extremist groups. The situation in Pakistan is not different either, as U.S. military aid that was intended to bolster Pakistan's counterterrorism capabilities has been criticised when it was diverted to internal political control, conventional posturing, or security force actions viewed as suppressing domestic opposition (Mulnick et al., 2016; Watts, 2015).

Overall, the military aid around the world has been treated with mixed feelings. One perspective supports the military aid. However, another perspective opposes the military aid. It is against this background that this study seeks to examine the implications of increasing military aid on arms sales and production.

Consequences of the Military Aid on Arms Sales and Production

Increasing global military aid has generated intense debate in recent years, owing to what is at stake for international peace and security. It can be argued that the United States military aid has been used in some countries such as Nigeria, Egypt, Israel, Saudi Arabia, Afghanistan, Colombia, Iraq, Pakistan and the Philippines, among others, contrary to the memorandum signed by the US and the respective recipient nations, since the October 7, 2023 attack on Israel by Hamas and Hezbollah terrorists and the swift response of Israel to the attack in self-defense. The United States military aid to Israel has been heavily criticised on many fronts, especially by Arab nations such as Lebanon and Yemen, just to mention a few, on the grounds that weapons provided to the Israeli military were used against the unarmed civilian population in Gaza, who were mostly women and Children. However, this criticism has been debunked by the Israeli government, which argued that the Israeli military's primary targets were mainly armed terrorists.

In Nigeria, the United States military aid to combat the Boko Haram insurgency were not spared from outright criticisms from Human rights activists and Human rights organisations such as Amnesty International who have argued that Nigeria military used the military aid it received from the United States to violate the rights of civilians who were mostly women and Children (De Luce, et al 2015). Explains the US decision to withdraw its military hardware from Nigeria under the leadership of former President Goodluck Jonathan. However, after some review of the state of insecurity in Nigeria, the United States provided some military aid to Nigeria under specific conditions that the rights of the civilian population must be protected (Cooper et al, 2016; Pham, 2012).

In a related development in other parts of the world, similar conditions were given to Pakistan by the United States in a bid to access its military aid (Kronstadt, 2012). For instance, military aid worth \$300 million was withheld from Pakistan for failing to effectively combat al-Qaeda and the Taliban. Also, involvement of Pakistan in illegal procurement of nuclear weapon materials and the inability of Pakistan to return to democratic governance were key in the United States military withdrawal of aid from Pakistan (Kronstadt, 2012; Ryan, 2016).

In addition, the Philippines has received military aid from the United States to fight insurgency in recent years. However, there is a decline in United States military aid to the Philippines following records of human rights violations under the leadership of President Rodrigo Duterte (Katigbak, 2016). This shows that donor countries still have some considerable levels of control over how recipient nations can use their military equipment. But one of the challenges to the donor countries control over their military aid, as to do with the willingness of countries such as the US, Russia, China, Iran and North Korea among others to provide alternative military aid were a given donor country failed to do so, even when purpose of the refusal to give military aid by a particular donor country was justified. For instance, when the United States withdrew its military aid to the Philippines for gross violation of human rights, while China saw it as an opportunity to consolidate its relationship with the Philippines by providing the Philippines government with the sum of 100 million Yuan (\$14.4 million) in military aid under President Rodrigo administration (Grevatt, 2016). This competition for military aid delivery among donor nations has implications for international security, as donor nations, in a bid to consolidate their relationship with old allies or develop new friendships among nations, tend to use military aid as a tool to lure nations into friendship, and nations that refuse such military aid are considered enemies.

However, following Russia's invasion of Ukraine in February 2022, which led to the imposition of various sanctions on Russia by the US and Western nations. Iran was among the leading countries to provide Russia with the HESA Shahed 136 drone, also referred to as Geran-2 in Russia, or Kamikaze drone or suicide drone, and other weapons. Also, North Korea and Belarus equally provided weapons and military forces to aid Russia's invasion of Ukraine. Ukraine also received short and medium-range weapons from the United States and its Western allies. It is important to state here that the continuous receipt of military aid by both Ukraine and Russia has sustained the war since 2022. This has a negative implication on international security, given the number of countries involved in the provision of military aid and continuous revenue from arms manufacturing firms (Binnie, 2021).

Nevertheless, the Israel-Hamas and Israel-Hezbollah war has increased global revenue from the sales of arms globally. Studies of the Stockholm International Peace Research Institute (SIPRI) as of 2 December 2024 have shown that an estimated 100 defence industries made an estimated \$632 billion in 2023, which represents an increase of 4.2 per cent compared to the total revenue made in 2022. Besides, in 2023, significant numbers of arms industries that were declining before 2022 were resuscitated in 2023. In the United States, arms industries generated \$133 billion in revenue, which represented half the total arms revenues earned by the Top 100 arms industries globally. This represents a 2.5 per cent increase above the 2022 revenue earned. Though, as of 2018, the United States was the home to the top 100 arms firms in the world (Stockholm International Peace Research Institute, 2024).

In 2023, out of the 41 United States arm firms, among which are Lockheed Martin and RTX, among others, 30 of the arm firms experienced an increase in their revenues 2023. In Europe, 27 arms firms that were among the top 100 in the world in countries such as Germany, Sweden, Ukraine, Poland, Norway and the Czech Republic, among others, witnessed increased revenue of \$133 billion in 2023, signifying a 0.2 per cent increase in revenue earned in 2022. However, two Russian arms production companies that are among the top 100 arms production firms experienced an increase in revenues of 40 per cent, estimated \$25.5 billion (Stockholm International Peace Research Institute, 2024).

In the same vein, available data from Firstpost in 2023, as shown in Table 1 below, shows that four of the leading United States arms production companies made significant profits during the Israel-Hamas war.

Table 1: Showing the United States Defence Stocks Increase during the Israel-Hamas War in 2023

Company	Percentage
Northrop Grumman	12%
General Dynamics	9%
Lockheed Martin	8%
Raytheon Technologies (RXT)	4%

Source: Firstpost (2023)

Table 1 above shows that the United States arms company Northrop Grumman made a 12 per cent stock rise; General Dynamics made a 9 per cent stock rise, and Lockheed Martin made an 8 per cent stock rise in 2023, while Raytheon Technologies (RXT) made a 4 per cent stock rise in 2023. Therefore, Northrop Grumman made more stock rise than other arms production companies in the United States. The implication of the above finding is that the Israel-Hamas war has financial benefits to the United States' arms companies. Hence, it can be argued that bringing the war to an end tends to have negative consequences on the US defence stock.

There is an ongoing debate within the fields of international relations and strategic studies regarding the primary beneficiaries of the United States' substantial defence expenditures. Scholars and policy analysts question whether these enormous allocations primarily serve the strategic security interests of the U.S. and its allies, bolster the influence of the military-industrial complex, or disproportionately benefit major defence contractors and political elites (Carafano, 2020; SIPRI, 2023).

Table 2: Showing Beneficiaries of Military Spending in the United States (2023-2024)

Company	Arms Revenue (2023)	Arms % of Total Revenue	Total Revenue (2024)
Lockheed Martin	\$60.8 B	90%	\$71.0 B
Raytheon Technologies (RTX)	\$ 40.7B	59%	\$80B
Northrop Grumman	\$ 35.6 B	91%	\$ 41.0B
Boeing	\$31.1 B	40%	\$66.5 B
General Dynamics	\$30.2 B	71%	\$ 47.7B
L3Harris Technologies	\$14.8	76%	\$ 21.3B
Huntington Ingalls (HII)	\$ 9.3 B	81%	\$ 11.5B
Leidos	\$8.7 B	50%	\$ 16.7B
Booz Allen Hamiton	\$ 6.9 B	65%	\$ 10.7B

Source: Stockholm International Peace Research Institute (SIPRI), (2023).

Table 2 above revealed that U.S arms companies such as Lockheed Martin, Raytheon Technologies (RTX), Northrop Grumman, and Boeing collectively account for a substantial share of global arms sales, positioning the United States as the single largest supplier of military hardware in the world (SIPRI, 2023). This further shows the dominance of the United States defence contractors in global arms production and trade, which has significant implications for international peace and security. Therefore, the concentration of arms production by U.S companies reflects not only the economic strength of the U.S. defence sector but also its strategic role in shaping global security dynamics. It can be argued that war is no longer a government affair, but rather a business affair, as private arms companies in the U.S make a profit from arms production and distribution.

It is also important to note that, arms production and sales strengthen U.S. alliances and defense partnerships in the international system, especially in enhancing interoperability among NATO members and other strategic partners through the sales of F-35 fighter jet, Patriot missile systems, and advanced naval technologies, which the U.S has used to consolidate its influence in Europe, Middle East, and Asia-Pacific (Carafano, 2020).

However, large-scale arms transfers also contributed to regional arms races and militarisation, particularly in volatile regions such as the Middle East and South Asia. For example, U.S. arms sales to Israel, Saudi Arabia, and the United Arab Emirates have triggered competitive procurement by rival states like Iran, thereby aggravating regional tensions and undermining diplomatic conflict resolutions (Sharp, 2023; SIPRI, 2023).

Subsequently, the Israel-Hamas war has further implications on arms production in other parts of the world, as shown in Table 3 below:

Table 3: Showing Rise in Defence Spending during the Israel-Hamas War in 2023

Region/Countries	Percentages of Budgetary Increment
Europe	13%
Japan	7%
South Korea	7%
India	6%

Source: Firstpost (2023)

From table 3 above, the Israel-Hamas war has led to an increase in defence spending in Europe to 13 per cent, Japan 7 per cent, South Korea 7 per cent and India 6 per cent. The implication of the above finding shows that the Israel-Hamas war has led to arms proliferation and armament in other parts of the world. This has consequences for global peace and security.

Besides, 23 arms companies in Asia and Oceania that are among the top 100 in the world witnessed a 5.7 per cent increase in arms revenue totalling \$136 billion. Moreover, four South Korea-based arms companies experienced a 39 per cent increase in arms revenues estimated at \$11.0 billion. In Japan, arm companies' revenue rose by 35 per cent, estimated at \$10.0 billion. It is pertinent to note that the rising threat of China and North Korea to South Korea and Japan, respectively, triggered local demand for arms, as well as the Russia-Ukraine war. Consequently, 6 of the top 100 arms companies in the Middle East had an increasing revenue growth of 18 per cent, estimated at \$19.6 billion. Subsequently, the war between Israel and Hamas, as well as Israel and Hezbollah, necessitated the increasing arms revenues of the three companies in Israel that were among the leading 100 arms companies in the world, estimated at \$13.6 billion. In Türkiye, arms revenues increased by 24 per cent, estimated at \$6.0 billion, as a result of the demand for arms due to the ongoing Russia-Ukraine war. For instance, Türkiye's Baykar produces armed uncrewed aerial vehicles (UAVs) that have been commonly used in the war in Ukraine, accounted for around 90 per cent of its arms revenues in 2023, which increased Türkiye's arms sales revenue by 25 per cent, estimated at \$1.9 billion (Stockholm International Peace Research Institute, 2024).

China's arms production firms were not left out, as 9 of the Chinese arms companies recorded a 0.7 per cent increase in arms revenue estimated at \$103 billion. In India, 3 of its arms production firms that were among the top 100 arms firms in the world experienced a revenue increase of over 5.8 per cent, estimated at \$6.7 billion. Taiwan's sole arms manufacturer, NCSIST, ranked among the top 100 arms manufacturing firms in the world, and made a 27 per cent increase in its arms revenues estimated at \$3.2 billion. The United Kingdom also benefited from the global increase in arms revenue. For instance, the UK witnessed an over 16 per cent increase in revenue estimated at \$2.2 billion (Stockholm International Peace Research Institute, 2024).

Furthermore, another implication of increasing United States military aid with a focus on arms transfers/sales is the issue of corruption that characterises the purchase and sales of arms, that have generated intense criticisms, given the increasing rate of insurgency in the world despite huge financial resources committed to arms procurement. For example, in Nigeria, in a bid to combat insurgency, huge budgetary provisions are made for the procurement of arms, but in the end, are diverted into the pockets of a few political and military elites. Today, the United States is beginning to tie its military aid to respect for human rights, democracy and the fight against corruption, among others.

Studies have shown that U.S. military aid was diverted or misused in countries such as Afghanistan, Iraq, and Nigeria. This has further raised questions about end-use monitoring and

accountability mechanisms (Mulnick et al., 2016; Watts, 2015). These challenges highlight the security dilemma: while U.S. military aid aims to enhance political stability and counter common threats such as terrorism, the arms are used to intensify insecurity among adversaries, leading to a cycle of militarisation.

In addition, the economic interests of the United States military–industrial complex complicate the strategic calculus. Arms companies benefit immensely from sales of arms, which may incentivise sustained arms proliferation levels in conflict-prone regions, by distorting the line between strategic necessity and profit-driven policies (Stohl and Grillot, 2010).

It can be argued that the military aid has been treated with mixed feelings. However, it has been argued that the military aid was to ensure the survival of the state and safeguard the sovereignty of any state. Yet, the goal of military aid has been beneficial to arms companies around the world and has undermined international security.

On the whole, this has a long-term implication on international security as arms manufacturers have ensured that the wars and other forms of armed conflicts remain unabated, because the sustainability of these wars and armed conflicts tends to ensure increased revenue for the arms manufacturers.

Conclusion

This study seeks to examine the implications of military aid on arms sales and production. The study revealed that the implications of increasing military aid on international peace and security include the violation of human rights, humanitarian crisis, corruption and increased revenue for arms manufacturing firms across the globe, among others. Currently, the United States remains the world's largest provider of military aid. Although some countries, such as the United States and Britain, have given military aid based on some conditions. Some of these conditions turn out to be appropriate, while some are not appropriate as they tend to violate the laid-down principles upon which the military aid was given. To this end, making military aid effective without violating global security and at the same time achieving the goals it was meant for has been problematic, given what is at stake in recent years on how military aid has been used for other purposes contrary to their primary objectives. It is against this backdrop that this study makes the following recommendations as a measure in addressing the growing challenges posed by increasing military aid to international security.

Recommendations

- a. The United Nations Security Council should employ a more democratic approach to the ongoing war between Israel-Gaza war and Russia and Ukraine to produce a win-win outcome for the interests of international peace and security, as against the interests of conflict merchants/entrepreneurs/profiteers from military aid.
- b. The United States should streamline and redefine the conditions for military aid in order for recipients to use the military aid for the purpose for which it was requested. This will help to address the growing state of military aid used by political leaders to suppress their citizens. Also, the United States should streamline its policies on the sales of arms/ arms transfers in order to regulate arms proliferation across the globe.
- c. The United Nations Security Council should develop a global framework for the regulation of military aid and other military assistance in order to ensure that nuclear weapons do not fall into the hands of non-state actors such as terrorist groups.

d. The United States remains the leading country in the world in military aid support. Therefore, the United States Government should reduce its global military aid to assist countries that are facing serious security threats, such as the fight against terrorism and other global security threats.

e. The United Nations Security Council (UNSC), in collaboration with the United Nations General Assembly (UNGA), should ensure the enforcement of the Arms Trade Treaty (ATT) by the UN member states. This will, among other things, promote universal ratification and stricter implementation of the ATT to regulate the flow of conventional weapons

References

- Al-Rasheed M (2016) Why did Riyadh cancel \$4 billion in aid to Lebanon? Al-Monitor. Available at: <https://www.al-monitor.com/originals/2016/02/saudi-arabia-lebanon-withdraw-aid-military-iran.html>
- ARA News (2017) Germany worried about use of German weapons in intra-Kurdish conflict. 7 Mar. 2017.
- Badri-Maharaj S (2016) China's growing influence in the Caribbean. Institute for Defence Studies and Analyses, 3 Aug. 2016.
- Bario M (2013) Somalia receives arms from Djibouti. Somali Destitute Medical Aid Society, 5 Apr. 2013.
- Barrington L and Abdallah I (2016) Lebanese military gets US, British aid for defending border with Syria. Reuters. Available at: <https://www.reuters.com/article/world/lebanese-military-gets-us-british-aid-for-defending-border-with-syria-idUSKCN0WX1UM/>.
- Binnie J (2021) *Global arms trade trends and U.S. security cooperation*. Defense Analysis Journal 45(3): 210–225.
- British Foreign and Commonwealth Office (2013) United Kingdom strategic export controls: Annual Report 2012. London: Stationery Office.
- British Ministry of Defence (2016) Gifting Minute—Gift Additional Ammunition to Kurdistan, Letter to Parliament, 30 June 2016.
- Carafano JJ (2020) Future of U.S. security cooperation: Strategic priorities and challenges. Heritage Foundation. Available at: <https://www.heritage.org/>
- Chicago Council Survey (2023) Chicago Council Survey September 7-18, 2023.
- Congressional Research Service (2023) *U.S. security assistance to Ukraine*. CRS Report. Available at: <https://crsreports.congress.gov>
- Cooper H and Searcey D (2016) After years of distrust, US military reconciles with Nigeria to fight Boko Haram. New York Times. Available at: <https://www.nytimes.com/2016/05/16/world/africa/boko-haram-nigeria-us-arms-sales-warplanes.html>
- Copper JF (2016) *China's Foreign Aid and Investment Diplomacy*, vols. I–III (Palgrave Macmillan: New York, 2016).
- Covenant of the League of Nations (1919) Article 11 of the covenant of the league of nations 1919.
- De Luce D and O'Grady S (2015) US to boost military aid to Nigeria for Boko Haram fight. Foreign Policy. Available at: <https://foreignpolicy.com/2015/07/16/u-s-to-boost-military-aid-to-nigeria-for-boko-haram-fight/>
- Defense Security Cooperation Agency (2023) Fiscal year 2023 annual report. U.S. Department of Defense. Available at: <https://www.dscamilitary.com>
- Deutsche Welle (2016) Germany delivers 16 armored vehicles to Jordan as part of defense aid package.

- Dolamari M (2016) Germany sends 70 tons of weapons to Kurdistan Peshmerga. Kurdistan24. Available at: <https://www.kurdistan24.net/en/story/368724/Germany-sends-70-tons-of-weapons-to-Kurdistan-Peshmerga>
- Dominguez G (2017) Turning the tide. Jane's Defence Weekly.
- El Universo (2016) Asistencia militar de China a Ecuador llegaría a \$ 29 millones' [Military assistance from China to Ecuador would reach \$ 29 million]. Available at: <https://www.eluniverso.com/noticias/2016/08/22/nota/5757456/asistencia-militar-china-pais-llegaria-29-millones/>
- Ellwood T (2016) Parliamentary under-secretary (Foreign and Commonwealth Office), answer to Syria: Lebanon: Written Question 31299, 29 Mar. 2016.
- Firstpost (2023) Defence spending soars across the globe.
- Firstpost (2023) U.S Support for Ukraine wanes.
- Gay JA (2014) Five Iranian weapons of war Israel should fear. National Interest. Available at: <https://nationalinterest.org/feature/five-iranian-weapons-israel-should-fear-10920>
- Grevatt J (2016) China offers USD500 million in military aid to Philippines. Jane's Defence Industry,
- Gul A (2017) Russia to host wider regional conference on Afghanistan. Voice of America. Available at: <https://www.voanews.com/a/russia-to-host-wider-regional-conference-on-afghanistan/3709818.html>
- Hammond P (2016) Secretary of state for foreign and commonwealth affairs, gifting of equipment to the 4th land border regiment of the Lebanese armed forces. Written Statement HCWS463.
- International Crisis Group (2017) Colombia's peace deal: What's next? International Crisis Group. Available at: <https://www.crisisgroup.org/latin-america-caribbean/andes/colombia/colombias-peace-deal-whats-next>
- Katigbak J (2016) US to provide \$180-M aid to Philippines next year. Philippine Star. Available at: <https://www.philstar.com/headlines/2016/10/08/1631489/us-provide-180-m-aid-philippines-next-year>
- Kiel Institute for World Economy (2022). Aid data 2022.
- Kronstadt KA (2012) Pakistan: U.S. foreign aid conditions, restrictions, and reporting requirements, congressional research service (CRS) report for congress R42116. US Congress, CRS: Washington, DC.
- McInnis KJ and Lucas NJ (2015). What is 'building partner capacity '? Issues for congress, congressional research service (CRS) report for congress R44313 US Congress, CRS: Washington, DC.
- Moroney JDP, Thaler DE and Hogler J (2013) Review of Security Cooperation Mechanisms Combatant Commands Utilize to Build Partner Capacity. Santa Monica: RAND Corporation.
- Mulnick, R., et al. (2016). Security assistance and governance challenges in fragile states. Center for Strategic and International Studies.
- Mulnick S and Goodman C (2016) Unexamined risks: The Pentagon's military aid abroad. Security Assistance Monitor, Center for International Policy.
- Pannier B (2015) Tajikistan: The far outpost of great powers. Radio Free Europe/Radio Liberty.
- Peel M, Kynge J and Haddou L (2016) China draws Cambodia closer in diplomatic embrace. Financial Times.
- Pham JP (2012) Boko Haram's evolving threat. Africa Security Briefs, (20): 1–8.
- Ryan M (2016) Pentagon withholds \$300 million in military aid to Pakistan. Washington Post.
- Serrano M (2019) The FARC and peace negotiations in Colombia. Journal of Peacebuilding & Development, 14(2): 181–187. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1542316619853847>
- Sharp JM (2023) U.S. foreign aid to Israel. Congressional Research Service. Available at: <https://crsreports.congress.gov>
- Sokhean B (2016) China to help modernize military, defense minister says. Cambodia Daily.
- Stockholm International Peace Research Institute (SIPRI) (2012) Islamist advance. Jane's Intelligence Review, Dec. 2012, pp. 16–17.

- Stockholm International Peace Research Institute (SIPRI) (2023) Top 100 arms-producing and military services companies, 2022. Available at: <https://www.sipri.org>
- Stohl R and Grillot S (2010) *The International Arms Trade*. Cambridge: Polity Press.
- The Tribune (2016) China gives \$1.2m to buy military equipment. Available at: <http://m.tribune242.com/news/2016/jan/29/china-gives-12m-buy-military-equipment/>
- United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime (2021) Colombia: Coca cultivation survey 2020. UNODC. Available at: <https://www.unodc.org>
- United Nations (1945) Article 1 of the United Nations Charter in 1945.
- Var V (2016) China's influence in Cambodia. *Khmer Times*.
- Watts S (2015) U.S. military aid and its unintended consequences. RAND Corporation.
- Watts S (2015). *Identifying and Mitigating Risks in Security Assistance for Africa's Fragile States* Santa Monica: RAND Corporation.
- Wezeman, S. et al, (2016) International arms transfers. *SIPRI Yearbook 2016*, pp. 587–94.
- Williams D (2009) Israel seeks discount on two German warships. *Reuters*. Available at: <https://www.reuters.com/article/economy/israel-seeks-discount-on-two-german-warships-idUSGEE5AN12E/>

the

peet

Journal of Politics and Development

ISSN 2632-4911

Volume 15 ■ Number 2 ■ Summer 2025

